

The ethical dilemmas of Filipino seafarers in cruise line industry: A basis for action plan

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Abstract

The study aims to explore the dilemmas experienced by Filipino seafarers in the cruise line industry. Purposive sampling was used in phenomenological approach to examine the lived experiences of Filipino seafarers. There is a constraint of ten (10) seafarers who worked in the cruise line industry and had a difficult situation. The researcher collected data from the respondents' written and verbatim reports on their demographic information and interviews with seafarers in order to address the research problem. The average age of mariners was shown to be thirty-five (35) years old. This statistic is backed further by the fact that the majority of seafarers interviewed are between the ages of thirty-one and forty, followed by twenty-one to thirty, and then fifty-one to sixty. This study also claims that the majority of seafarers examined had an average term of service of one to ten years, followed by eleven to twenty years. Additionally, the survey findings revealed that the majority of respondents worked in the food and beverage department, followed by the stewardship departments, and lastly the deck, engineering, and secretarial departments. It also demonstrates that the majority of those questioned are college graduates, with the average being a college undergraduate and the least being a high school graduate. Also according to the findings of this survey, the majority of participants earned between 28,000 and 67,000 pesos each month. The researchers have identified four (4) common or super ordinate themes from the dilemma that was discussed by every participant: (1) Family Ties; (2) Health Concerns; (3) Faith and Temptation; and (4) Work – related problems. After completing the study, a developed action plan was produced that will be utilized for Filipinos.

Keywords: Filipino Seafarers; Cruise line Industry; Lived Experiences; Common themes; Action Plan

1 Introduction

Today's seafarers deal with a variety of intricate dilemmas at work. In order to be effective and morally valiant in dealing with these moral issues, one requires a wide range of decision-making abilities. Such complicated issues include a wide range of circumstances and may escalate conflicts between workplace values and workers itself, which are due to disparities between a person's upbringing and the workplace culture. Some of complicated issues are sexual harassments, family problems, about health, work, and other factors that make every seafarer decide and chose between two or more option, in order to reach their goal or their intention. Despite the fact that numerous researches has been carried out to explore the types of problems workers encounter, not enough is understood about these circumstances or what influences a worker's response to such difficulties. The rationale and mental processes under a reaction to the dilemma are still relatively unknown, even though previous research has been successful in identifying ethical difficulties faced by workers. Although there are frameworks to describe how circumstances, attitudes, and other factors may affect choices, there is no explanatory theory to describe how particular people make moral decisions in particular circumstances [1].

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Theoretical concepts about the causes and consequences of ethical dilemma have been established by philosophers, psychologists, sociologists, academics, and members of the corporate world. According to [2] Separation from spouse and family has been identified as one of the most major sources of stress for seafarers, with separation from family being one of the most prominent "stress" variables driving a choice to reduce scheduled sea service. Since the maritime profession has existed, the challenge of forming a family of seafarers, raising a kid, having a healthy marriage, or building a strong parent-child connection with the child has been well documented.

[3] stated that long work shifts, long-term contracts (usually 3 months or more), distance from home, bad social life on board, and fear about not obtaining enough medical treatment in case of diseases on board are the key factors leading to the decrease of seafarers' mental health. Cultural differences and linguistic obstacles can make it difficult to form social interactions on commerce ships, heightening feelings of loneliness. This claims that having problems on long distance relationships and/or family ties that requires them to decide or have a final decision affects their job performance and also their health, not just mental but also physical.

Several moral judgment tests have been developed, but studies suggest that persons who perform well on these tests may not always perform well when analyzed in scenario-based circumstances. The contrast between "should" and "would you do" can be used to explain this [4]. Varying answers to the questions "what should I do" and "what would I do" were generated in hypothetical scenarios. [5] also examined moral judgment in hypothetical situations and found that moral decision was lower in actual circumstances than in hypothetical ones. Understanding the dilemmas faced by seafarers is essential since it provide us with perspective into what it's like to work in a global sector in a variety of ways. Understanding the social portrayals of the work and daily lives of cruise industry sailors reflects current definitions of labor and employment in a globally relevant business from an economic and social perspective. Given the recent enormous development of cruise ship travel, this is especially important.

This study aims to identify challenges related to seafarers remains an important issue within the cruise line industry as work-related issues continuous to prevail that further creates situation for seafarers to choose between two or more "lesser" options. One of the key issues addressed by the International Transport workers' Federation concerns wages and salary. There are instances where an employer is incapable or unwilling to pay its workers. While the majority of crew members eventually get paid, some never do, and others must wait for their last payment for even months or years. The concerned ship owners aim to preserve the functioning of their ship with the least amount of investment possible by using pressure techniques, assurances of future payments, or minor advances on the total sum due. Sadly, manpower agencies frequently engage in efforts to convince crew to work longer hours without compensation. Even though the crew members in question initially paid them for the pleasure of working on board the ship—which is against the law—they do nothing to help if there are issues and often won't help crew members who haven't been paid.

In addition to the difficulties outlined above, when seafarers are injured, ill, or pass away, they rarely receive the full compensation required by the law and the contract since their employers does not hesitate to use its extensive resources to restrict its liability. The decision makers typically rely on the doctor's biased diagnosis of the company designated doctor over that of their personal doctor when their designated heirs submit a claim for remuneration for death, disability, or illness, in determining whether or not cause of death is work-related, or the gravity or grading of the injury. In many cases, the seafarer signs papers without even reading it, freeing his employer from any claims, demands, or causes of action. He is frequently tricked into accepting ex-gratia, meager sums under the guise that his health has nothing to do with his job or any other factor he does not understand. He is frequently aware that his rights being violated, but it leaves a question on how he should challenge his employer without compromising his chances of finding work again. The seafarer is then forced to sign his contract of employment, an agreement of commitment, even if it is replete with confusing clauses, assumptions, and intricacies that he does not understand, and it contains terms and conditions that are more beneficial to his employer [6]

Whenever faced with those situations mentioned above, seafarers tend to feel afraid to complain or to seek help. This is due to the fear of being summarily dismissed or blacklisted. Historically, blacklisting has been seen as the misery of seafarers, particularly in the Philippines. The most frequent alleged "offense" stated on the lists for people who were banned is "ITF (The International Transport Workers' Federation) involvement." which most likely occurred as a result of the seafarer looking for help to recover unpaid pay. Being blacklisted entails complete loss of employment, loss of income, and denial of the right to engage in one's line of work. Additionally, it may result in family separation, loss of the seafarer's home, inability to support children's education, and other consequences. This kind of situation places a seafarer to face a certain dilemma in his life. He is in a situation wherein he has to choose between raising his concern to get what he deserves or being blacklisted by the company that poses life consequences.

With that being said, this research aims to focus and highlight the dilemmas experienced by our local seafarers in the cruise line industry. This will be accomplished by interviewing Filipino seafarers who recently experienced being placed in a situation wherein he has to make a choice, imposing great effect to his life. In this way, a wide understanding about cruise ship situations and retention issues in the industry will be systematically discussed. Furthermore, the intention of this work is to capture data across a broad range of experiences as seafarers recant their facing and dealing with ethical dilemmas. The research moves to analyze dominant factors in determining reaction and response. This thesis will progress from defining an ethical dilemma to examining the experiences of these seafarers with ethical dilemmas in the cruise line industry. Critical incident interviews were conducted to determine types of experiences encountered, thoughts and emotions experienced throughout the situation, process of identifying options and action taken, along with the seafarer's reasoning associated with their action (or decision to take no action). The results of this qualitative study will be then used to create an action plan that will further resolve future dilemma issues of seafarers and other line of industry. This study further enhances our understanding of decision making and action in the face of an ethical dilemma. Ultimately, the underlying rationale for conducting this research is the assumption that with a better understanding of the dilemmas seafarers face and how they respond, we can better prepare solutions and response to deal with these complex situations in the future.

Moreover, the scope of this study includes review of the literature, methods, data analysis, findings, and conclusions and recommendations for future research. This thesis will advance our knowledge of the topic as dominant themes are identified to extend theory.

Seafarers have always been associated with a life of adventure and danger. For many, the sea is a place of opportunity, where they can earn a good living and provide for their families. But for some, the sea is also a place of great challenges, where storms can whip up suddenly and where shipwrecks in their own lives happen. Due to these challenges, seafarers, most of the time, steps in a situation wherein they face a certain dilemma while they are on board.

[7] highlighted that the most common issue on board is homesickness, which is followed by exhaustion, family problems, discrimination, poor communication, and poor interpersonal relationships at work. Aside from those common problems, there are certain issues and experiences from Filipino seafarers that are needed to be address. The succeeding texts will further discuss the experiences of seafarers that made them faced dilemma in the cruise line industry.

From a recent report of Philippine Daily Inquirer, to prevent the seafarers from their mental anguish or a significant amount of emotional pain, agony, torture, or suffering that could make a crime worse or be the focus of a lawsuit for compensation or wrongful death pain and suffering, and their permanent disfigurement, the company are responsible for their health and security to make up for the crew member's lost wages from the past and the future. For a disabled crew member who had accidents, the employment contract only permits a maximum reimbursement of \$29,480 for they Once a member of the crew or their loved ones receive a death or disability payment, they forfeit their right to file a claim against the cruise line employer and operator. The rules of the International Labor Organization are violated by this (ILO). Such pitiful salaries diminish the worth of a Filipino's life.

Another case revealed by [8] was an experience from a victim named Lito Asignacion, a Filipino seafarer who was a senior engine fitter working aboard a bulk carrier when hot water overflowed a tank due to hazardous working conditions on board, causing major burns to his abdomen and legs. In the burn units in a hospital in U.S.A., the crew member endured extensive and painful medical care. Asignacion was treated and underwent skin grafting for burns covering 35% of his body. Mr. Asignacion continued to receive medical treatment and surgeries after returning to the Philippines. He is today disabled, unemployed, and scarred for life. The burned crew member's employer claimed that because of his grade 14 disability, he was only eligible for 3.74 percent of USD \$50,000 under the POEA.. According to the labor board, the shipping company offered the disabled crew member \$25,000 "out of sorrow and generosity". This case shows, the Filipino labor system allows maritime companies and insurance providers to desert those seafarers who have made significant sacrifices and endured a tremendous deal of suffering for their families. Making fun of a system that favors the wealthy while failing the injured and struggling seafarer by imprisoning attorneys who fight for increased rights for seafarers and allowing maritime businesses to postpone payment of arbitration decisions.

In another area, [6] mentally anguished seafarers request disability or death claims due to work-related situations, they complain about biased decisions made by company doctors. He stated that companies frequently argue that they are not obligated to pay benefits in the majority of seafarer cases for disability or death benefits claims by citing medical reports from the company-designated physician that the seafarer's illness is not related to his or her work, that he or she is fit to work, or that compensation is limited to a lower amount based on a low disability grading

In connection with the issue being tackled, the International Commission on Shipping highlighted the blacklisting issue and abandonment of seafarers. The commission was brought to the attention of cases where seafarers were being defrauded of their agreed-upon earnings as well as where seafarers had significant back pay owed but were unwilling to protest or ask for assistance for fear of being immediately terminated or placed on a blacklist. Being placed on a blacklist result means complete loss of one's job, income, and ability to practice one's trade. Additionally, it may result in family separation, loss of the seafarer's home, inability to support children's education, and other consequences. The worst-case scenario that may happen is that crew members who were owed significant amounts of wages being abandoned in a foreign port as a result of a ship owner's financial collapse

2 Theoretical Framework

This study is based on ideas and models such as Rest's Ethical Decision-making Model. Rest (1986) developed a theoretical framework of ethical decision-making that includes moral awareness, moral judgment, moral intention, and moral action, with a focus on the process of recognizing and resolving an ethical challenge. Rest claims that when presented with an ethical problem, people go through a decision-making process that includes thinking through these four components. Individuals progress from moral awareness to recognition of a moral situation leads to moral judgment, which evaluates options and outcomes, moral intent, which determines how one plans to behave, and finally moral action, which is the actual conduct in the scenario. that failure to make an ethical judgment might occur from a failure at any stage of the process of the decision making.

In this model, consciousness is the beginning stage. Before considering potential actions, the person must be able to recognize that a situation has ethical implications. Another framework used by this study is the Jones' Issue - Contingent Model of Moral Intensity. Jones' model is based on James Rest's theory of four-component ethical decision-making (1986). To understand a person's attention to ethical issues, Jones (1991) created a theory of moral intensity based on Rest's theory, arguing that various elements of the moral situation - what he collectively designated as moral intensity - impact individuals' decision-making abilities. The concept of moral intensity as a construct that reflects the level of issue-related moral necessity in a circumstance explains this dilemma.

This is a significant study and model since it dissected the circumstance into its constituent parts in order to determine which ones would have the biggest influence on a person's capacity for moral judgment. The moral intensity of the situation will affect a person's capacity to discern whether a situation has potential moral implications, according to [9], who also believed that moral intensity factors affect each phase of the decision-making process. Jones made this claim using Rest's model of ethical decision-making.

2.1 Conceptual Framework

In a study examining the ethical dilemmas faced by Filipino seafarers in the Cruise Line Industry, several independent variables were identified. The first independent variable focused on the demographic profile of the respondents, aiming to understand how different characteristics might influence their decision-making processes. The second variable delved into the various situations and experiences where the seafarers encountered dilemmas during their time at sea. Under the second variable, subcategories were explored to gain a deeper understanding of the seafarers' experiences. The first subcategory examined the ethical issues or dilemmas they encountered and how they responded to them ethically. It sought to uncover the moral challenges they faced and the subsequent behaviors and actions they displayed after making a decision. The second subcategory focused on the ethical judgment and intent of the seafarers, aiming to assess their thought processes and motivations behind their choices. Lastly, the third subcategory investigated how organizational factors influenced their decision-making, recognizing that external factors within their work environment might impact their ethical considerations. Ultimately, the study aimed to develop an action plan based on the ethical dilemmas faced by Filipino seafarers in the Cruise Line Industry. By understanding the independent variables and their relationship to the dependent variable, researchers sought to create a comprehensive strategy that would address these dilemmas and promote ethical behavior among seafarers in the industry.

The purpose of this study is to cast light on the ethical dilemmas encountered by Filipino seafarers in the cruise line industry by addressing a series of questions. The demographic profile of seafarers who have confronted difficulties will be investigated first. This includes age, gender, work position, years of service, educational attainment, and monthly income. By comprehending these demographics, a clearer picture of the individuals confronting ethical challenges in the industry can be constructed. The study will then examine the situations and circumstances in which mariners have encountered dilemmas while at sea. It seeks to identify the specific ethical issues or dilemmas they have encountered, as well as their ethical behavior after reaching a decision. In addition, it seeks to comprehend the seafarers' ethical judgment and motivation when confronted with these dilemmas. The study will conclude by examining the

organizational factors that influence their decision-making, taking into account the impact of external factors in their workplace. The ultimate objective of this research is to devise a plan of action based on the dilemmas encountered by Filipino cruise line workers. The purpose of this study is to contribute to the improvement of seafarers' ethical decision-making abilities by shedding light on the underlying issues and factors at play. It also endeavors to foster a greater appreciation for the difficulties and dilemmas faced by seafarers.

This study is significant for a variety of stakeholders. The findings will aid seafarers in enhancing their ethical decision-making abilities and gaining a deeper comprehension of the challenges they face. Families of seafarers can also benefit from the study by advocating for regulations and initiatives that address the mariners' well-being and health. The research will aid maritime students in acquiring knowledge about the cruise line industry and the challenges they may face in the future. Administrators and maritime institutions can use the research to establish partnerships and develop scientifically-based solutions to maritime industry issues and dilemmas. The research will contribute to the university's research portfolio and will benefit students and the community. In addition, future researchers investigating the challenges encountered by cruise ship crews can use this study as a valuable resource.

It is essential to note the study's scope and limitations. Participants in this study are ten Filipino seafarers who are at least 18 years old and have encountered an ethical dilemma at work. These participants were chosen using techniques of purposive sampling and were prepared to discuss their experiences openly. This method permits qualitative researchers to maximize limited resources by selecting individuals or groups with relevant knowledge or experience.

3 Material and methods

This study will utilize Phenomenological Research design. This type of research is a great tool to understand different experiences of the participants. That will provide the researchers individual lived experiences by knowing and understanding their assumptions [10]. The qualitative research interview method applied in this study displays in greater detail the influences and mental processes of each participant. The research's common themes offered insights into how moral decisions are made in the setting of companies, and practitioners can utilize these insights to better understand ethical decision-making and strengthen ethical cultures in their own workplaces. The findings will also contribute to the body of knowledge regarding the influences on ethical behavior and the context of circumstances. A qualitative research study was conducted.

The samples of this study consists of ten (10) Filipino seafarers in cruise line industry having at least 18 years of age and have faced an ethical dilemma in the workplace and were willing to talk openly about their experiences. Purposive sampling is a sort of non-probability sampling in which researchers choose members of the general population to participate in their surveys based on their own opinions. It is also referred to as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling.

Purposive sampling involves choosing samples from the total sample size depending on the survey taker's or researcher's assessment. To put it another way, a purposive sample is gathered in accordance with the specifications of the test, survey, or research for which it will be utilized [11]. To gather the required data needed for the study, the researchers will used semi - structured interview questionnaires. The content validity of the questionnaire was assessed by the teacher and these questionnaires were made up of open-ended questions that have been designed as precisely as possible in order to maximize the effectiveness of the surveys. A collection of questions with flexible phrasing and terminologies that are asked in any sequence are used in semi-structured interviews. The researcher tries to cover areas of interest in semi-structured interviews with introductory inquiries and probes. Depending on the participant's response, questions were modified as necessary.

The questionnaire was enhanced and modified for its applicability to the respondents. It contains two (2) sections. The first section, comprises with the demographic profile of the respondents, Their name, age, gender, address, work position, and number of years in service [12, 13]. The second part includes interview questions that deal with their Ethical issues or dilemma faced by the seafarers and their Ethical behavior after making a decision. Also, their Ethical judgment and intent of the seafarers will also be asked. And lastly, the organizational factors that affect their decision.

The proponents of this study set aside time and effort to decide on a questionnaire for the intended Participants. The questionnaire was made to include questions that would be useful to our Participants in obtaining reliable information. The researchers will conduct an interview with them, utilizing the questions from the modified questionnaire to assist them explain and convey their narrative about their difficulty. The researchers will explain each question to them so that they answer it appropriately and do not stray too far from the question. Each interview will be transcribed and further analyzed.

Finally, the data were synthesized to present the overall narrative of what was discovered throughout these interviews. For the data analysis, the researchers will use thematic analysis. According to [14], thematic analysis is a qualitative data analysis process that entails reading over a data collection such as transcripts from in-depth interviews or focus groups, and looking for patterns in meaning throughout the data to extract themes. Thematic analysis is an active process of reflexivity in which the researcher's subjective experience is crucial to deriving meaning from evidence.

After having interviews, the researchers will read and analyze all of their answers and be familiarize with it. After reading and familiarizing, they will look for those answers that shares the same thought and will come up , and generate different themes that will help them find The results, to conclude and have recommendations. will contribute to the body of knowledge and identify potential topics for further study.

4 Results and discussion

4.1 Demographic Profile of the Participants

The survey results demonstrate that the average age of the seafarers is thirty-five (35) years old. The majority of participants appear to be in the ages of between thirty-one to forty (31 to 40), that is, six (6) participants or sixty percent (60%) of the total participants. This is followed by seafarers having an age between twenty-one to thirty (21 to 30), which comprises of three (3) participants or thirty percent (30%) of the whole sample. This observation is followed by the least number of participants, the age bracket of fifty-one to sixty (51 to 60), which is them composed of only one (1) participant, gaining ten percent (10%) of the total participants. Finally, it is also observed that none of the participants interviewed falls into the age bracket of forty-one to fifty (41 to 50). This study posits that the majority of seafarers who were interviewed fall between the ages of thirty-one to forty, followed by twenty-one to thirty and then fifty - one to sixty. This information also shows that even after the age of fifty, which is considered an age for retirement preparation and time where health complication arises, some seafarers continue to practice their career and competence. This perspective is quite intriguing in light of other possible options, such as land-based employment or starting a business. Therefore, employers may wish to investigate, via future research, the factors that may affect the motivation of seafarers to remain with their current employer.

Figure 1 Age of the Participants

[15] mentioned in their study that seafarers continue to choose their career even as they get older due to the implementation of regulations and advantages provided to seafarers, although some tend to seek out other opportunities if given the chance. Therefore, while it is accurate that workers are more likely to choose seafaring as a career as they age, employers can retain employees by implementing advancement opportunities for all seafarers, as a lack of promotion opportunities onboard can lead seafarers to pursue careers on land [16].

The survey results demonstrate that the majority of participants, composed of five (5) participants or fifty percent (50%), came from the food and beverage department. This specific department is comprised of the interviewed individuals, namely, two (2) chefs, two (2) waiters and one (1) cook.

This data is then followed by two (2) participants or twenty (20%) of the sample who came from the stewardship department. This specific department is comprised of the interviewed individuals, namely, one (1) laundry attendant and one (1) security officer. Next, it was also observed that the deck department is composed of only one (1) participant which is identified as a Bosun Officer. Same goes with the clerical department having one (1) IT Tech Analyst interviewed. Lastly, the researchers also identified one (1) participant from the engineering department having the job of being a plumber.

Figure 2 Work Position of the Participants

These results revealed that the majority of participants were most likely to work in the food and beverage department, followed by the stewardship departments, and finally the deck, engineering, and clerical department. This portion may be of interest to some seafarers who are interested in career advancement opportunities. After completing his evaluation, educational, and training requirements, a cook may consider pursuing his ambition to become a head chef. The same holds true for a plumber working alongside with other engineers, who may be motivated by the privilege and benefits of a higher-ranking position, eventually pursue a college education, and diligently work towards his goal. This section may shed light on future research on the motivations and aspirations of seafarers based on their current job positions. Such inquiries could provide employers with information regarding the length of time that their employees may consider, as well as the staff turnover based on the job gratification that these individual people are experiencing [17].

4.2 Demographic Profile in terms of Number of years in Service

Figure 3 Number of years in service

The survey results demonstrate that the average service length of the seafarers interviewed is six (6) years. The majority of participants appear to be serving the industry from one to ten (1 to 10) years since they entered the cruise line, that

is, nine (9) participants or ninety percent (90%) of the total sample interviewed. This is followed by seafarer serving the industry from eleven to twenty (11 to 20) years since the first day entering the cruise line, that is, one (1) participant or ten percent (10%) of the total. This study posits that the majority of seafarers who were interviewed fall between average length of service from one to ten years, and followed by eleven to twenty years of service.

Intriguingly, the intentions of seafarers can be investigated further in future studies, as it is not only the period that seafarers devote to maritime that is considered to be the primary concern; rather, implementations of financial, collaborative, and land-based possibilities and skills can be illuminated, taking into account the timescale that seafarers take into account while they remain in service. As current data indicates that some seafarers tend to prolong their service beyond twelve (12) years, [18] revealed that seafarers tend to have few savings due to a lack of feasible strategies for achieving financial objectives such as cost of pension plan, encompassing their daily living, medical, and other expenditures from the day they stop working and for the remainder of their lives. This issue can be disconcerting to employers, as seafarers may be more concerned with monetary compensation than with the significance of their work in terms of their careers, the quality of service they offer, and their well-being. Even though it's true that income could make seafarers want to continue their "career" and work as long as possible, another factor could be the need to know for sure what kind of service they can give.

Figure 4 Educational Attainment

The survey results show that the average educational level of the seafarers surveyed is College Undergraduate. The majority of participants appear to be college graduates, accounting for six (6) of the total sample interviewed (60%). This is followed by ten percent (10%) of seafarers who were high school graduates. According to this survey, the majority of seafarers asked are college graduate.

A preparatory bachelor's degree is not necessary for a seafarer, although it may be useful for a variety of reasons. One of the key reasons is that the degree will provide a seafarer with a more in-depth understanding of the maritime industry, including its history and legislation. This knowledge can assist a sailor when dealing with other crew members and speaking with clients and consumers [19]. Additionally, a preparatory bachelor's degree can provide a seafarer with the technical skills and knowledge required to operate and maintain the various systems and equipment aboard a ship. Lastly, a preparatory bachelor's degree may lead to various career opportunities in the marine industry, such as working as a maritime consultant or doing maritime-related research [20].

The survey results show that the (50%) monthly of the seafarers surveyed is 28,000 pesos to 67,000 pesos. Followed by those seafarers that have 68,000 pesos to 107,000pesos which is twenty percent (20%). Also, twenty percent (20%) for those who has monthly salary of 188,000 pesos to 227,000 pesos. Lastly, are those participants, or the seafarers that has 108,000 pesos to 147,000pesos monthly salary which is ten percent (10%). These results revealed that the majority of participants were most likely to receive monthly income of 28,000 pesos to 67,000 pesos.

[21] state that numerous studies in the literature advocate for a high-paying employment strategy to address the maritime profession's bad working circumstances, which have a severe influence on seafarers' physical and mental health. As a result, there is a scarcity of qualified seafarers. Yet, increasing wages alone cannot guarantee acceptable working conditions; other fundamental governing concepts and rights in the workplace also play crucial roles. In this

scenario, analyzing the impacts of wage alone would fail to uncover the fundamental problem and would prohibit the study's findings from being generalized to all seafarers.

Figure 5 Monthly Salary

Persistent irritation and stress may be exceedingly detrimental to seafarers' physical and mental health. Constant psychological stress might impair decision making. Additionally, repetition of the same mistakes, decreased job efficiency, reclusive behavior/neglecting interaction with crew members/withdrawal symptoms, refusal to follow instructions, negligence.

4.3 Emerging Themes

The researchers have identified four (4) common or superordinate themes from the dilemma that was discussed by every participant: (1) Family Ties; (2) Health Concerns; (3) Faith and Temptation; and (4) Work – related problems. These themes are accompanied by verbatim and/or documented participant reports.

Table 1 Emerging Themes and Participant Responses

Emerging Themes	Number of Participants	Percentage	Rank
Family Ties	3	30%	1.5
Faith and Temptation	3	30%	1.5
Health Concerns	2	20%	2.5
Work – related problems	2	20%	2.5
Total	10 Participants		

As presented in the table above, dilemma about family ties and faith towards their relationship tied in the first spot having both 3 out of 10 responses. It was then followed by health concerns and work-related problems, also tied at the third spot. According to [2], family matters such as conflict or event can also have an impact on seafarers, causing over thinking. It is a significant factor for seafarers, resulting in a rush to return home. As an example, having a conflict in a relationship at home can turn into a big problem because it can affect the mentality of a seafarer. As cited by the International Transport Workers' Federation, even good news (for example, having a newborn baby, celebrating a birthday, etc.) can lead to over emotion due to over thinking. Even if there is a conflict or an event, family matters can have an impact on the seafarers' ability to work and may result in them being sent home.

Furthermore, how many times have we heard the cliché, "A girlfriend in every port?" Seafarers face numerous temptations, including infidelity, alcohol, and drugs, among others. Because they are cooped up in their ship with other seafarers, peer pressure is high [22].

4.3.1 Family Ties

This theme is characterized by dilemmas experienced by the participants wherein their decisions appear to be influenced with their family relationships. When the participants were asked with the question, "Describe a set of circumstances at work in which you faced a dilemma or stressful situation." The participants answered with the following responses:

4.3.2 Illustrative texts

[S1]: *"Hindi inaasahan noon, 2 weeks bago ako umalis, 'yung anak kong panganay na lalaki ay naaksidente. On-work siya non sa QC Katipunan (bilang) delivery boy ng isang fastfood at medyo magulo sitwasyon ng isip ko noon dahil nga malala ang naging kalagayan ng anak ko. Malaki ang magiging gastos kaya kailangan ko rin makabalik ulit sa barko pero kailangan nila ako dito sa Pinas para maalagaan 'yung anak ko dahil ang asawa ko naman ay nasa Hongkong at ang kasama niya lang sa bahay ay anak kong bunsong babae."*

[S2]: *"Kasama ko sa trabaho ang pinsan ko, nauna siya ng ilang taon, at laging napapagalitan sapagkat mainitin ang ulo sa kusina at minsan may pagkareckless kumbaga. Minsan ay napagalitan sya at nasabihan ng last warning. May nagawa na naman siyang mali that time na 'di niya sinasadya. Nagagyan niya ng sesame seeds yung spinach salad na dapat ay wala. Dahil sa hind ipag-iingat at pagmamadali, nagreklamo yung customer at nakarating sa manager. Sinabi nya sakín lahat at nakiusap na akuin ko yung kasalanan para hindi na siya mawalan ng trabaho. Ako naman, 'di ko alam kung papayag ba ko o hindi ko aakuin kasi baka ako naman ang manganib."*

[S3]: *"I got a telegram saying that my grandmother from Nueva Ecija, who was like my mother because she was my mother's best friend, had passed away from a heart attack. When I was in elementary school, if I felt uneasy, I would call her, and she would always give me something to cheer me up. We haven't spoken or laughed together in almost a decade. Although the ship won't be here until later this afternoon or tomorrow morning, I still want to go."*

After hearing their testimonies, the participants were asked with the follow up question, "How did you respond with the situation? What helped you decide?" The participants answered with the following responses:

[S1]: *"Pinili kong sumampa at ang nakatulong sa akin dito para ako'y makapagdesisyon ay yung magulang ko at pati narin ang asawa ko, kasi pinakahangad namin mag asawa ay mabigyan sila ng magandang buhay, masuportahan pangangailangan at kung ano andiyan. Ang aking ama at ina, pati mga kapatid, na pwede rin malapitan ng anak ko para magabayan sila habang wala kami ng asawa ko."*

[S2]: *"Inako ko (yung kasalanan) at na-warning lang ako, laking pasasalamat sa akin noon dahil inako ko sapagkat naawa na din ako, at alam ko na warning pa lang naman at unang beses. (Sa pagdedesisyon), sarili ko lang, kasi kailangan ko agad magdesisyon at kakausapin agad yung manager. Siguro pati yung pinsan ko, kasi hindi din naman ako nito pababayaan, at dahil alam na niya ugali ng manager namin."*

[S3]: *"Although I really love her, I have job to do and am unsure of what to do. While crying to go to her, I'm also eager to get to work. My mother advised me on what to do, and my uncle warned me that if I choose to remain with her and lose my job, my grandma will be furious. They advised praying to God and talking to him in order to help us be okay, as well as my grandmother."*

This theme examined the difficulties that seafarers faced, such as the problems, illness or death of a family member. Looking at the death and accident concerns, these problems cannot be resolved immediately while they are separated from their families. Some participants tend to worry about the welfare of their family members while they are away. Depending on the individual, some seafarers report or do not describe their own conditions to their loved ones when these problems occur.

[S3]: *I do recall that day since I skipped lunch and didn't move for several hours. Since I have nowhere to go, I ultimately made the decision to grieve in private while doing laundry at work."*

It was discovered that some seafarers inclined not to discuss their situations and sufferings while onboard because they do not want their family and friends to become anxious or concerned. On the contrary hand, some seafarers tend to remind their relatives about the nature of their work and how their hard-earned income may be considered

4.3.3 Health Concerns

This theme is characterized by dilemmas experienced by the participants wherein their decisions appear to be influenced by their health situation. When the participants were asked with the question, “Describe a set of circumstances at work in which you faced a dilemma or stressful situation.” The participants answered with the following responses:

[S4]: *“Dati, kakatapos ko lang sa duty ay papunta ako sa kwarto para maglinis at magpahinga, pero sa paghubad ko ng damit, ay napaatras ako at natumba. Buti nalang na ituon ko ang braso at hindi napuruhan ng ulo. Simula noon ay madalas nang sumasakit braso ko. Napansin ko habang tumatagal sumasakit, nung nagbakasyon ako, nagpacheck up na ako at lumalala na daw linear fracture sa braso. Pinayuhan ako na huwag muna masyadong gumawa ng mabibigat kasi may kalakihan yung fracture, at nagreseta na lang ng gamot. Simula noon, nag-ingat na ako. Minsan nai-ituon ko at nakakapagbuhat ako kaya masakit lalo, nagiging maselan na, kaya napaisip ako kung babalik pa ba ako sa barko, sabi ng anak ko huwag na daw, sila na lang daw bahala sa amin kasi nagtatrabaho na din naman sila, e’ ang sa akin naman ay may pamilya din sila na binubuhay.”*

[S5]: *“I am excited na nga kasi magbabakasyon na ko ng ilang buwan, I already told my family that I will be with them nasa wakas. Madami kaming plano but suddenly, kinausapa ko ng manager naming na kung pwede mag stay na muna kasi they will be needing more employees at maraming guests. We need money din naman kasi bukod sa sarilikong pamilya, nagbibigay pa rin ako sa parents ko. Sinabi ko sa wife ko na possible na mag-stay muna ako for a while, nalungkot siya pero she understands naman. I have the chance to be with them pero mapapatagal pa, pero makakaipon naman kami. Miss ko na sila, ‘di ako sanay na hindi nauwi pagbakasyon.”*

After hearing their testimonies, the participants were asked with the follow up question, “How did you respond with the situation? What helped you decide?” The participants answered with the following responses:

[S4]: *“Napagdesisyonan ko nanga na mag-retire na, tapos na naman mga anak ko, at may ipon na ako, pero hindi madali yung desisyon na iyon sapagkat kailangan pa rin namin ng pagkakakitaan. Pamilya at doctor ang tumulong sa pagpili ko ng desisyon. Pinipilit na din ako mag retire ng pamilya ko na para sa aking kalusugan din naman.”*

[S5]: *“I chose to be with them, I decided to choose my mental health since I know that it will affect my overall productivity, homesickness can be just a shallow reason but for me I love to have quality time with my family because they are my strength and weakness. I may be able to save more money if I choose to stay but my mind, and heart will suffer. I know that I can earn it (money) after my vacation, so I had my leave.”*

According to [23], seafarers are at the greatest risk for stress-related physical and mental conditions. International Trade Federation discovered that seventy-five percent (75%) of seafarers in the Philippines reported knowing a depressed coworker. [24, 25] discovered that Filipinos appear to associate anxiety within a social context, which can be discussed by the interrelated self-concept prevalent in Filipino culture.

4.3.4 Temptation and Sexual Harassment

This theme is characterized by dilemmas experienced by the participants in relation with sexual harassment and interaction they experienced. When the participants were asked with the question, “Describe a set of circumstances at work in which you faced a dilemma or stressful situation.” The participants answered with the following responses:

[S6]: *“Isang gabi noon, day-off ko kasama mga katrabaho hindi maiwasan uminom mga kasama kong iba binata pa at hindi naman malayo sa edad. Sa ‘di inaasahan, pagnakakainom maraming pwedeng mangyari. Dahil may nangyari sa amin nung babae nadala ako ng tukso na nangyari nung gabing yon alam kong mali pero nagawa ko pa rin. Hindi ko alam kung ano gagawin dahil maayos kami ng asawa ko at ilang sampa na ako noon lang una akong nakagawa na mangano (to have sex) ng babae. Natakot ako ng sabihin dahil ayaw kong maghiwalay kami pero mabigat sa pakiramdam lalaki ako lalo maayos aming pagsasama”*

[S7]: *“Isang pasahero ang kinausap ako at akala ko ay makikipagkaibigan lang noong wala kami sa duty. Tapos niyaya at inalok niya ako ng malalawang gawain kapalit ng pera. Akala ko nung una ay lalaki pero silahisata. Nailing ako at nagalit sa kanya pero kinausap nya ako at tinaasan ang alok kaya ako naman ay nakumbinsi. At syempre pera din yon kase nung*

mga panahon na 'yon, gusto ko mabili mga bagay na hindi ko nabibili dati, kumbaga dagdag ipon din. Pero bago ko tinanggap ay inisip ko din sapagkat baka gawain na niya ito at baka may AIDS na, pero nasilaw ako sa pera kaya tinanggap ko. Hanggang sa nakasanayan ko na nagawin iyon. Isa pa ay hindi ko alam kung sasabihin ko sa magulang ko na nagkasakit ako, o magpapagaling na lang ako, nakakahiya kasi e."

[S8]: *"Nung unang sampa ko, yung system manager naming na lagi kong nakakaharap sa tuwing magrereport ako ng inventories at updates ay masyadong malikot ang kamay, na laging nanghihiyo ng katawan na para bang may gusting gawin, pero hindi nangyari yon. Noong una nagalit ako pero tinakot niya ko namawawalan ng trabaho kung ganon ugali ko. Hindi naman siya nanghihiyo ng maselang bahagi ko pero nakakailang at nandidirina din ako, 'di ko na alam gagawin kaya nasabi ko sa mga kasama ko. Sabi nila pagpasensyahan ko na daw kasi hanggang doon lang naman, kasi pwede daw ako matanggal sa trabaho kasi malapit siya sa nakakataas. Sabi ko baka naman this time mabigyan na siya ng leksyon, baka pwede kong subukan na magreklamo. Ilang gabi din akong hindi makatulog."*

After hearing their testimonies, the participants were asked with the follow up question, "How did you respond with the situation? What helped you decide?" The participants answered with the following responses:

[S6]: *"Hindi naging madali pero tinapangan ko loob ko dahil gusto ko buo ang pamilya. Isang beses nagkamali ako, dapat gawin na magbago kung sabihin ko man sa asawa baka possible nahiwalayan ako. Pambababae yon, alam ng asawa at magagalit siya sa akin kung hindi ko sabihin. Andun yung bigat at konsensya ko lagi kong isipin na baka may magsumbong kase mga katrabaho ko sa barko ay mga malapit sa aming magasawa."*

[S7]: *" Dahil nga nakakahiya di ko sinabi sa mga kasama ko, pero parang nakakakutob nasila. Sarili ko lang yung pinagkatiwalaan ko kasi mahirap na."*

[S8]: *"Pinag-isipan kong mabuti, pero sabi ko kapag tinuloy ko ang reklamo ko, kawawa naman yung mag-ina ko, mag-iisang taon palang baby ko at kailangan ko mag-ipon, kaya hinayaan ko na lang. Tumigil din naman siya nung hindi ko na pinapansin panghihiyo nya na parang wala lang, pero ilang buwan ko din tiniis."*

[26] revealed that Filipino seafarers experienced a more negative work environment, with higher levels of harassment, laissez-faire governance, and poor safety, despite experiencing stronger team cohesion and perceiving their captains to be more genuine.

4.3.5 Work – related problems

This theme is characterized by dilemmas experienced by the participants in relation with their problems they encounter in work and with their colleagues. When the participants were asked with the question, "Describe a set of circumstances at work in which you faced a dilemma or stressful situation." The participants answered with the following responses:

[S9]: *"Plumber ako at minsan e may nangyari ng hindi inaasahan, sa loob ng engine room ay may nag-apoy. Nagpanic ako noong una pero pinakalma ko sarili ko. Nag-raise na ang fire alarm signal at nahirapan ako mag decide kasi hindi ko alam kung magpapakabayani ba ko para kunin yung portable foam extinguisher para maapula (ang apoy) o intayin ko na lang sila dahil delikado."*

[S10]: *"When I was working, I felt stressed out from carrying heavy loads, and because of tension from other personal issues, I got into an argument with a deck OS Crew who also lived in our area in Baritan . Because he neglected to mention the replacement of the spare components in the report, I have spoken some bad words to him. It took me hours to realize that I had overreacted that particular moment, and I am aware of it today. I also have personal issues at the time, which makes it simple for my wrath to flare up. Even though he is also at fault, but it is not how it should be. I had hoped that time would help things get better, but after a few days he stopped being as productive and continued to be angry with me even during our break. I'm not sure if I'll wait for us to be okay or if I'll apologize to him right away."*

After hearing their testimonies, the participants were asked with the follow up question, "How did you respond with the situation? What helped you decide?" The participants answered with the following responses:

[S9]: *"Sa takot ko na lumaki pa ang apoy at madaming mapahamak, kinuha ko yung foam extinguisher. Nagkaroon ako ng second degree burn pero natulungan ko naman na hindi kumalat yung apoy bago dumating na ang CE na mag-ooperate ng CO2 (fixed fire extinguishing system). Sa mga ganong klase ng emergency, sarili at lakas ng loob ang kailangan mo at tandan kung ano ang mga nasa training para magawa nang tama at ayos ang dapat gawin upang hindi napapahamak."*

Kasama na dito ang tiwala sa Maykapal, na alam kong kasama ko siya lagi, kaya malakas ang loob ko nasumubok para sa kaligtasan ng lahat.”

[S10]: “I have made up my mind to talk to him that enable us to be productive. I talked to my father about it because we often exchange updates before going to bed. Because of his mentality that he always wants to talk through and solve problems, he never wants anyone to be mad with him.”

Analysis shows that participants cope with or adjust to their work-related challenges primarily by trying to talk with respect to their coworkers; this approach is followed by empathizing with coworkers' conditions; inclination to technical knowledge and being a quick learner have also been noted as adaptation to work, as technical issues happen in the workplace.

5 Conclusion

The research study yielded several conclusions based on its findings. The interviews conducted with seafarers revealed that the average age of participants was thirty-five years old. Most participants were employed in the food and beverage department, followed by stewardship departments, and then the deck, engineering, and clerical departments. In terms of length of service, the seafarers interviewed had an average service ranging from one to ten years, with some having eleven to twenty years of experience. Education-wise, the majority of seafarers were college graduates, with the average participant having completed some college education and the least having a high school diploma. Regarding monthly salary, the study found that most participants earned between 28,000 and 67,000 pesos each month. Analyzing the interviews, the researchers identified four common themes that emerged from the discussions of dilemmas faced by every participant: Family Ties, Health Concerns, Faith and Temptation, and Work-related Problems. Participants generally focused on the advantages or pros when discussing the pros and cons of their choices. Moreover, when making decisions while on board, participants reported relying on their families for guidance and moral support.

In light of these findings, the researchers provided several recommendations. They suggest that employers should offer promotion opportunities for all seafarers to improve retention rates, especially as workers tend to choose seafaring as a long-term career as they age. Strengthening the connections between seafarers and their family members, such as siblings and parents, is also recommended to enhance well-being. Further studies are encouraged to gain better insight into seafarers' desires and goals, as well as their job satisfaction. Additionally, prioritizing the attainment of a diploma is suggested to enhance job opportunities and facilitate career progression. Providing training and workshops to improve seafarers' skills and abilities can increase productivity and open doors to wage and salary raises through promotions. Understanding how long employees contemplate staying with a company and the reasons for leaving can inform decision-making and retention strategies. Collaboration with implementing bodies and seafarers' support networks is advised to develop interventions, learning sessions, and training programs that strengthen coping mechanisms and promote workplace adjustments. Seafarers are recommended to identify their desired outcomes or goals when making decisions to facilitate weighing the pros and cons effectively. Lastly, decision-making should take into account various factors, including personal safety, the safety of others on board, and legal implications. Seeking guidance from fellow seafarers, maritime experts, the company's legal team, and one's family is encouraged, as decision-making as a seafarer can be challenging.

These conclusions and recommendations provide valuable insights into the ethical dilemmas faced by Filipino seafarers in the cruise line industry, aiming to enhance their overall well-being and improve their decision-making processes.

Proposed action plan for the dilemmas of Filipino seafarers in cruise line industry

General Objective: The main objective of this study is to understand and explore the dilemmas faced by the Filipino seafarers in the cruise line industry.

Specific Objectives:

1. Examine the link between seafarer's moral belief systems and ethical behavior.
2. Examine how seafarers reflect on the outcomes from the decision they have made.
3. Develop an action plan based on the dilemmas of Filipino seafarers in the cruise line industry.

Activity	Time Frame	Expected Outcomes
Discussion of the dilemmas encountered by Filipino seafarers in the cruise line industry.	4 - 5 days	To have a careful discussion of the dilemmas and challenges of Filipino seafarers.
Seminar and Workshop: Handling Long Distance Relationships while on board		To impart ideas and suggestions on how to handle long distance relationships between a seafarer and his/her family.
Mantal Health Consultation		To help seafarers who are having a hard time facing their problems.
Free HIV Testing and Seminar		To impart knowledge and awareness to seafarers about infectious diseases.
Team Building Activities		To build camaraderie between seafarers and their colleagues.

DAY 1	
Activity	Discussion of the dilemmas encountered by Filipino seafarers in the cruise line industry
Expected Outcomes	To have a careful discussion of the dilemmas and challenges of Filipino seafarers
Proposed Necessities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Rent for Venue - Fee for speakers - Food for participant and speakers. - Printing expense
Outsourced Materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monoblock Chairs - Projector and white screen - Sound System - Health Kit - Tables - Stage Design - Technical Set Up

DAY 2	
Activity	Seminar and Workshop: Handling Long Distance Relationships while on board
Expected Outcomes	To impart ideas and suggestions on how to handle long distance relationships between a seafarer and his/her family.
Proposed Necessities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Rent for Venue - Fee for speakers - Food for participant and speakers. - Printing expense
Outsourced Materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monoblock Chairs - Projector and white screen

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sound System - Health Kit - Tables - Stage Design - Technical Set Up
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DAY 3	
Activity	Mantal Health Consultation
Expected Outcomes	To help seafarers who are having a hard time facing their problems.
Proposed Necessities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Rent for Venue - Fee for professionals. - Food for participant and speakers. - Printing expenses
Outsourced Materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monoblock Chairs - Sound System - Health Kit - Tables - Technical Set Up

DAY 4	
Activity	Free HIV Testing and Seminar
Expected Outcomes	To impart knowledge and awareness to seafarers about infectious diseases.
Proposed Necessities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Rent for Venue - Fee for speakers - Food for participant and speakers. - Printing expense
Outsourced Materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monoblock Chairs - Projector and white screen - Sound System - Health Kit - Tables - Stage Design - Technical Set Up

DAY 5	
Activity	Team Building Activities
Expected Outcomes	To build camaraderie between seafarers and their colleagues.
Proposed Necessities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Rent for Venue - Food for participant and facilitators. - Printing expense

Outsourced Materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monoblock Chairs - Projector and white screen - Sound System - Health Kit - Tables - Stage Design - Technical Set Up - Materials for activities.
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Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of Conflict of interest

The author declare that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this research. The author has no financial or personal relationships that could influence or bias our work. The sole objective is to present accurate and unbiased findings in the pursuit of scientific knowledge.

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